

Political ideology, dark tetrad, and types of intuition among adults

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Abstract

Political Ideology has been termed as an individual perspective, idea or belief about political or social information. Factors like personality traits, brain structure, thinking style, environment may influence political ideology. Various western research has shed light on association of political ideology, dark tetrad traits and intuition among adults. But few have looked at relationship from Indian perspective. This correlational study aims to understand the relationships between political ideology, dark tetrad traits, and types of intuition among adults in India. The sample of 220 adults were employed through convenient sampling. This study utilized three instruments - Political Ideology Scale by Puthillam and others (2021), Short Dark Tetrad (SD4) by Paulhus and others (2020), Types of Intuition Scale (TIntS) by Pretz and other (2014). Key findings include purity-based cultural norms having significant correlations with psychopathy, machiavellianism, and sadism traits, while obedience to hierarchical authority was linked to narcissism and machiavellianism. In terms of intuition, obedience to authority was positively correlated with inferential intuition and negatively with affective intuition. Economic ideology was negatively associated with holistic-abstract and positively with affective intuition. Machiavellianism was associated with inferential and holistic-big picture intuition, while psychopathy and sadism were linked to holistic-abstract intuition. Narcissism was positively associated with inferential intuition.

Keywords: Political Ideology; Dark Tetrad; Intuition; Adults; India

1. Introduction

India is the country with diverse population and complex political culture which are influenced by different historical, social and cultural factors. Unlike Western society, which often focus on Individualistic culture, Indian society focused on collectivistic culture which in turn influence political scenario in India. The research findings about political ideology from western and other eastern countries cannot be applied in India due to difference in how government functions, and political views or ideologies, voting behavior.

Political Ideology is the concept that “political opinions and attitudes are linked together in a coherent interconnected system” [1]. According to Erikson and Tedin (2019) [2], it is belief about structure of society and how to achieve it. The purity-based cultural norms (norms) refer to normative beliefs such as religion, dowry, and different culture-related issues which include items like “I don’t think people should be allowed to marry outside their religious communities.” The obedience to hierarchical authority (Hierarchies) refers degree to which one believes that hierarchical institutions and leaders should be respected, and followed. The economic ideology refers to people belief in economic activity relating to government [3, 4].

Paulhus and Williams (2002) [5] introduced the term Dark Triad in psychology which study machiavellianism, psychopathy and narcissism in unity. It was due to high usage of term Sadism and trying to correlate it with Dark Triad traits and study as a “Dark Personality” Dark Tetrad (DT) got introduced. Paulhus, Buckels, Trapnell and Jones gave 28 item scale to measure DT where machiavellianism, psychopathy, narcissism and sadism were also called as crafty, wild,

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special and mean [6]. Each DT traits play some role in political ideology. Narcissism traits make an individual seek authoritative role [7, 8], while Machiavellianism, traits help in strategizing to achieve personal goal [9, 10]. Psychopathy traits often characterized by lack of concern for others that can cause negative consequences in politics [11]. Sadism traits often involve getting enjoyment out of others suffering which can make an individual take wrong decision towards minorities [12].

Intuition has been termed as acquiring insight without the conscious reasoning or thinking [13]. Pretz and Totz in 2007 gave three classifications of Intuition – holistic, inferential and affective. It was based on two majorly used scales Rational-Experiential Inventory (REI) and Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI). Affective intuition refers judgement based on hunch or strong sense of emotional feelings [14]. Inferential intuition refers to quick judgments which become instinctual due to repeated practice [15]. Holistic intuition refers to decision based on bottom-up, data-driven process, which includes broad perspective, diverse information (holistic-big picture), and focus on abstract information (holistic-abstract) [14].

The various researches have suggested complex relationship between political ideology and DT traits mostly in western countries. Studies by Jonason (2014) [16], Lilienfeld et al. (2014) [17] suggests that Dark Tetrad traits like narcissism and Machiavellianism were positively associated with right wing ideology. But these relationships are not strong enough, as other researches stated negligible or negative association between DT traits and right lean ideology [18]. Social Dominance Orientation (SDO) theory was usually linked with DT traits, especially narcissism and psychopathy traits which play role in authoritarian nature [19, 20], while Right-Wing Authoritarianism (RWA) theory had mixed results [18, 19]. Other factors such as cultural norms and how an individual perceive also play important role [21].

Researches have explored the relationship between political ideology and types of intuition. Jones (2011) [22] gave the intuitionist model that states moral intuitions may shape and limit our cognitive processes. Lytwyn (2012) [23] states no significant relationship between Sensing-Intuition (SN), Thinking-Feeling and political ideology. De Neve (2015) [24] showed how big five personality traits like openness to experience and conscientiousness play important role. In research Cognitive Reflection Test (CRT) has been used to show how right lean view was related with intuitive thinking, while left lean with reflective thinking [25].

There have been studies stating relationship between Dark Tetrad traits and different measures of intuition and personality [26, 27, 28, 29]. MBTI was weakly related with Sensation-Intuition (SN) and several dark personality traits [26], while no direct relationship between NEO traits and ACT intuition was present. Furnham and Crump (2005, 2014) [28, 29] associated HDS (dark side traits), NEO-PI, MBTI, and they were poorly related with SN dimension, but strongly with Thinking-Feeling. Openness to experience and extraversion was positively associated with intuitive decision-making style [30]. This study helps provide insight how norms and hierarchies, and economic ideology factors identified to be part of political ideology in Indian context link to dark personality traits and intuition.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Aim

The primary aim of this research is to understand the relationships between Political ideology dimensions, Dark Tetrad traits, and types of intuition among adults.

2.2. Research Design

The research design is a correlational with quantitative approach. This type of design helps in assessing whether the relationship exist between Political ideology dimensions, Dark Tetrad traits and Types of Intuition.

2.3. Objective

There were 3 objectives for this study:

- To find whether significant relationship exist between Political Ideology dimensions and Dark Tetrad traits among adults.
- To find whether significant relationship exist between Political Ideology dimensions and Types of Intuition among adults.
- To find whether significant relationship exist between Dark Tetrad traits and Types of Intuition among adults.

2.4. Hypothesis

Ho1 - There will be no significant relationship between Political Ideology dimensions and Dark tetrad traits among adults.

- Ho1a: There will be no significant relationship between Norms and Narcissism traits among adults.
- Ho1b: There will be no significant relationship between Norms and Machiavellianism traits among adults.
- Ho1c: There will be no significant relationship between Norms and Psychopathy traits among adults.
- Ho1d: There will be no significant relationship between Norms and Sadism traits among adults.
- Ho1e: There will be no significant relationship between Hierarchies and Narcissism traits among adults.
- Ho1f: There will be no significant relationship between Hierarchies and Machiavellianism traits among adults.
- Ho1g: There will be no significant relationship between Hierarchies and Psychopathy traits among adults.
- Ho1h: There will be no significant relationship between Hierarchies and Sadism traits among adults.
- Ho1i: There will be no significant relationship between Economic Ideology and Narcissism traits among adults.
- Ho1j: There will be no significant relationship between Economic Ideology and Machiavellianism traits among adults.
- Ho1k: There will be no significant relationship between Economic Ideology and Psychopathy traits among adults.
- Ho1l: There will be no significant relationship between Economic Ideology and Sadism traits among adults.

Ho2 - There will be no significant relationship between Political Ideology dimensions and Types of Intuition among adults.

- Ho2a: There will be no significant relationship between Norms and Holistic - Big Picture among adults.
- Ho2b: There will be no significant relationship between Norms and Holistic-Abstract among adults.
- Ho2c: There will be no significant relationship between Norms and Inferential Intuition among adults.
- Ho2d: There will be no significant relationship between Norms and Affective Intuition among adults.
- Ho2e: There will be no significant relationship between Hierarchies and Holistic - Big Picture among adults.
- Ho2f: There will be no significant relationship between Hierarchies and Holistic-Abstract among adults.
- Ho2g: There will be no significant relationship between Hierarchies and Inferential Intuition among adults.
- Ho2h: There will be no significant relationship between Hierarchies and Affective Intuition among adults.
- Ho2i: There will be no significant relationship between Economic Ideology and Holistic - Big Picture among adults.
- Ho2j: There will be no significant relationship between Economic Ideology and Holistic-Abstract among adults.
- Ho2k: There will be no significant relationship between Economic Ideology and Inferential Intuition among adults.
- Ho2l: There will be no significant relationship between Economic Ideology and Affective Intuition among adults.

Ho3 - There will be no significant relationship between Dark Tetrad traits and Types of Intuition among adults.

- Ho3a: There will be no significant relationship between Narcissism traits and Holistic - Big Picture among adults.
- Ho3b: There will be no significant relationship between Narcissism traits and Holistic-Abstract among adults.
- Ho3c: There will be no significant relationship between Narcissism traits and Inferential Intuition among adults.
- Ho3d: There will be no significant relationship between Narcissism traits and Affective Intuition among adults.
- Ho3e: There will be no significant relationship between Machiavellianism traits and Holistic - Big Picture among adults.
- Ho3f: There will be no significant relationship between Machiavellianism traits and Holistic-Abstract among adults.
- Ho3g: There will be no significant relationship between Machiavellianism traits and Inferential Intuition among adults.
- Ho3h: There will be no significant relationship between Machiavellianism traits and Affective Intuition among adults.
- Ho3i: There will be no significant relationship between Psychopathy traits and Holistic - Big Picture among adults.
- Ho3j: There will be no significant relationship between Psychopathy traits and Holistic-Abstract among adults.
- Ho3k: There will be no significant relationship between Psychopathy traits and Inferential Intuition among adults.
- Ho3l: There will be no significant relationship between Psychopathy traits and Affective Intuition among adults.
- Ho3m: There will be no significant relationship between Sadism traits and Holistic - Big Picture among adults.

- Ho3n: There will be no significant relationship between Sadism traits and Holistic-Abstract among adults.
- Ho3o: There will be no significant relationship between Sadism traits and Inferential Intuition among adults.
- Ho3p: There will be no significant relationship between Sadism traits and Affective Intuition among adults.

2.5 Sample

The sample size was 220 where females were 111 and males were 109. Most of the participants that is 109 belonged to the age group of 18 – 25 years, while 59 to 25 – 45 years, 40 to 45 – 59 years and 12 to 60 years. The sample collected from India through convenient sampling technique.

2.5.1 Inclusion criteria

- Adults aged 18-60 years old
- Male, female and third gender
- Resident of India (Indian Citizen)

2.5.2 Exclusion criteria

- Participants with physical disabilities
- Participants diagnosed with psychological illnesses.

2.6 Measures

2.6.1 Political Ideology Scale

A 34-item test was created by Puthillam, Kapoor, and Karandikar (2021) [4] for measuring political ideology in India, which has three dimensions - purity-based cultural norms (norms), obedience to hierarchical authority (Hierarchies), and economic ideology. It is rated using a seven-point Likert-type scale (1 - Strongly Disagree to 7 -Strongly Agree). The reliability of whole scale was .89, while norms had .90, hierarchies had .87, and economic ideology had .45. The scale had content and face validity and was for people aged range 18-64 [3, 4]. A higher score can be interpreted as more “conservative” or right leaning [21].

2.6.2 Short Dark Tetrad (SD4)

The scale by Paulhus, Buckels, Trapnell and Jones (2020) [6] contained 28 items that measure the four traits: psychopathy, machiavellianism, narcissism, and sadism, that together forms DT. It is a five-point Likert scale (1—Strongly Disagree to 5—Strongly Agree). A high score indicates a higher level of individual traits. The reliability for narcissism was of .83, .78 for Machiavellianism, .82 for psychopathy, and .82 for sadism and has satisfactory construct validity. Gangwar et al. (2023) [31] stated SD4 has reliability of .81 validated on 1011 Indian aged 15-39 years.

2.6.3 Types of Intuition Scale (TIntS)

This scale [15] consisting of 23-item measures three types of intuition given by Pretz and Tetz (2007) [14]: holistic, inferential, and affective. It is five-point Likert scale (1 -Definitely false to 5 - Definitely true.). Reliability of was acceptable (Holistic–Big Picture [HB] $\alpha = .73$, Holistic–Abstract [HA] $\alpha = .74$, Inferential $\alpha = .72$, Affective $\alpha = .76$) and it has satisfactory convergent and discriminant validity. Swaminathan and Rathnasabapathy (2024) [32] stated it has good reliability score .66 validated on 755 university students in India.

2.7 Procedure

Prior to initiating data collection, approval was gained through research proposal from college Department of Psychology. After obtaining approval, data was collected via google forms.

2.8 Statistical Analysis

IBM SPSS Statistics Version 25 was used to analyze the data. Non-parametric test spearman’s rank-order correlation was used to find the correlation.

2.9 Research Ethics

This study followed all the APA ethical guidelines, including confidentiality, data protection, consent, voluntary participation. The participants were also informed that they could withdraw their participation whenever they wanted.

3. Results

The Kolmogorov–Smirnov normality test indicates that norms, economic ideology, DT traits, types of Intuition departed significantly from normality. Based on this, non-parametric test like spearman's rank-order correlation test was used to check the correlation.

Norms had very weak positive relationship with Narcissism traits ($r_s = 0.053, p = 0.437$), which was not significant. So, Ho1a was accepted. While it has weak, positive and significant relationship with psychopathy ($r_s = 0.368, p < 0.001$), and machiavellianism traits ($r_s = 0.201, p = 0.003$). But there was moderate, positive and significant relationship between sadism traits ($r_s = 0.416, p < 0.001$) and norms in adults. Hence Ho1b, Ho1c. Ho1d were rejected.

Hierarchies had weak positive and significant correlation with narcissism ($r_s = 0.275, p < 0.001$), machiavellianism traits ($r_s = 0.265, p < 0.001$). Hypothesis Ho1e, Ho1f were rejected. But it had very weak positive relationship with psychopathy ($r_s = 0.091, p = 0.179$) and sadism traits ($r_s = 0.054, p = 0.424$), which was not significant. So, Ho1g, Ho1h were accepted.

Economic ideology had weak negative relationship with machiavellianism ($r_s = -0.048, p = 0.483$), psychopathy ($r_s = -0.041, p = 0.545$), sadism traits ($r_s = -0.115, p = 0.087$). While it had weak positive correlation with narcissism traits ($r_s = 0.051, p = 0.455$), which were not significant. Hence, Ho1i, Ho1j, Ho1k. Ho1l were accepted (see Table 1).

Table 1 Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation between Political Ideology dimensions and Dark Tetrad traits among adults

SN.	Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	Norms	-							
2	Hierarchies	0.433**	-						
3	Economic Ideology	-0.284**	-0.082	-					
4	Political Ideology	0.832**	0.835**	-0.111	-				
5	Narcissism	0.053	0.275**	0.051	0.204**	-			
6	Machiavellianism	0.201**	0.265**	-0.048	0.283**	0.245**	-		
7	Psychopathy	0.368**	0.091	-0.041	0.278**	0.095	0.412**	-	
8	Sadism	0.416**	0.054	-0.115	0.279**	0.299**	0.264**	0.535**	-
9	Dark Tetrad	0.385**	0.225**	-0.065	0.372**	0.525**	0.658**	0.733**	0.785**

Note. ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.

Norms have very weak positive relationship with HB ($r_s = 0.011, p = 0.865$) and HA ($r_s = 0.129, p = 0.057$) which was not significant. But norms have very weak negative relationship with inferential intuition ($r_s = -0.019, p = 0.782$) and affective intuition ($r_s = -0.038, p = 0.571$), which was not significant. Hypothesis Ho2a, Ho2b, Ho2c, Ho2d were accepted.

Hierarchies had very weak positive relationship with HB ($r_s = 0.070, p = 0.300$), and very weak negative correlation with HA ($r_s = -0.064, p = 0.347$), which were not significant. Hypothesis Ho2e, Ho2f were accepted. Hierarchies had very weak negative correlation with affective intuition ($r_s = -0.141, p = 0.037$), and weak positive correlation between inferential intuition ($r_s = 0.309, p < 0.001$), which was significant. Hypothesis Ho2g, Ho2h were rejected.

Economic Ideology had very weak negative correlation with HB ($r_s = -0.025, p = 0.714$) and very weak positive correlation Inferential Intuition ($r_s = 0.031, p = 0.642$), which were not significant. So, Ho2i, Ho2k were accepted. Economic Ideology had very weak negative correlation with HA ($r_s = -0.133, p = 0.049$), and very weak positive correlation with affective Intuition ($r_s = 0.163, p = 0.016$), which were significant. Hence, Ho2j, Ho2l were rejected (see Table 2).

Table 2 Spearman’s Rank-Order Correlation between Political Ideology dimensions and Types of Intuition among adults

SN.	Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	Norms	-						
2	Hierarchies	0.433**	-					
3	Economic Ideology	-0.284**	-0.082	-				
4	Political Ideology	0.832 **	0.835 **	-0.111	-			
5	Holistic-Big Picture (HB)	0.011	0.070	-0.025	0.033	-		
6	Holistic-Abstract (HA)	0.129	-0.064	-0.133*	0.014	0.142*	-	
7	Inferential Intuition	-0.019	0.309**	0.031	0.170*	0.280**	-0.073	-
8	Affective Intuition	-0.038	-0.141*	0.163*	-0.086	-0.016	0.193**	-0.045

Note. ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

The narcissism traits were very weakly and positively correlated with HB ($r_s = 0.104, p = 0.123$), which was not significant. It has very weak negative relationship with HA ($r_s = -0.010, p = 0.880$), and affective Intuition ($r_s = -0.087, p = 0.199$), which were not significant. Hypothesis Ho3a, Ho3b, Ho3d were accepted. But narcissism traits had significant and very weak positive correlation with inferential intuition ($r_s = 0.180, p = 0.008$). So, Ho3c was rejected.

Machiavellianism traits had weak positive correlation with inferential intuition ($r_s = 0.322, p < 0.001$) and very weak positive correlation with HB ($r_s = 0.169, p = 0.012$), which were statistically significant. Hypothesis Ho3e, Ho3g were rejected. But machiavellianism traits had very weak positive correlation with HA ($r_s = 0.098, p = 0.148$), and very weak negative correlation with affective intuition ($r_s = -0.079, p = 0.243$), that was not significant. Hypothesis Ho3f, Ho3h were accepted.

Psychopathy traits had very weak and negative relationship with HB ($r_s = -0.048, p = 0.477$), and inferential intuition ($r_s = -0.012, p = 0.865$), which was not significant. It was positively correlated with Affective Intuition ($r_s = 0.028, p = 0.681$), but relationship was negligible and not significant. Hence, Ho3i, Ho3k, Ho3l were accepted. But psychopathy traits had significant and very weak positive correlation with HA ($r_s = 0.139, p = 0.039$). So, Ho3j there was rejected.

Sadism traits had weak positive correlation with HB ($r_s = 0.068, p = 0.315$) which was not significant. But it had very weak and negative relationship with Inferential Intuition ($r_s = -0.009, p = 0.900$) and Affective Intuition ($r_s = -0.115, p = 0.088$), which was not significant. Hypothesis Ho3m, Ho3o, Ho3p were accepted. Sadism traits had significant and weak positive correlation with HA ($r_s = 0.242, p < 0.001$). Hence, Ho3n was rejected (see Table 3).

Table 3 Spearman’s Rank-Order Correlation between Dark Tetrad traits and Types of Intuition among adults

SN.	Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	Narcissism								
2	Machiavellianism	0.245**	-						
3	Psychopathy	0.095	0.412**	-					
4	Sadism	0.299**	0.264**	0.535**	-				
5	Dark Tetrad	0.525 **	0.658 **	0.733 **	0.785 **	-			
6	Holistic-Big Picture	0.104	0.169*	-0.048	0.068	0.095	-		
7	Holistic-Abstract	-0.010	0.098	0.139*	0.242**	0.181**	0.142*	-	
8	Inferential Intuition	0.180**	0.322**	-0.012	-0.009	0.153*	0.280**	-0.073	-
9	Affective Intuition	-0.087	-0.079	0.028	-0.115	-0.072	-0.016	0.193**	-0.045

Note. ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

4. Discussion

The results of the present study provide insight into relationship between political ideology dimensions, Dark Tetrad (DT) traits, and types of intuition among adults in India. People with high DT will have high political ideology (right wing) was consistent with findings of [33, 34]. Our findings that there was some relationship between political ideology and DT traits were supported by findings of western studies [33, 34, 35, 36, 37] and Indian study by Puthillam and Kapoor (2022) [21]. But DT traits had negative relationship with norms, hierarchies [21], while Duspara and Greitemeyer's (2017) [33] states positive relationship was present, Bell et al. (2021) [36] showed narcissism was negatively related to political ideology. While Furnham and Cuppello (2024) [38], stated negative relationship between DT traits and political beliefs. But relationship was not strong indicating other factors also play [19, 39]. The lack of relationship between economic ideology and DT traits aligns with Bartolo and Powell (2024) [40], Bell et al. (2021) [36]. findings. However, some link was present [37].

Many studies showed there can be potential mediating or moderating factors influencing relationship between political ideology and dark personality traits [19, 24]. The social worldviews influence relationship between DT traits and SDO/RWA [19], and childhood trauma interaction with openness trait in shaping political ideology [24]. Additionally, people with dark personality trait may view politicians with same trait less negatively, which indicates some bias in how dark traits influence political preferences was present [41]. The Bardeen and Michel's (2019) [35] showed relationship between social and economic dimensions of political ideology with DT traits varies. There have been mixed findings due to different sample characteristics, measurement tool, analysis methods, and cultural difference [40]. While some studies focused on broad political view [16, 17, 18], and others looked at specific political view [20, 42].

The individuals who often make automatic intuitive judgments (inferential intuition) and rely less on gut feeling (affective intuition) tends to more obey higher authority, and information related to them. This is due using automatic reasoning to process political information. The inferential intuition positive association with political ideology indicates, when an individual is first exposed to any political information or ideas, they process it analytically. But after repeated exposure to it they use more mental-schema and pre-existing belief to make quick decisions. The high economic ideology relationship with low holistic abstract and high affective indicates individual who are less focused on abstract principles, and more on gut feeling tend to support strong right wing economic views. This is so because their belief was formed by specific experience and constant reliance on gut feeling rather than looking at broad picture. This result was supported by findings of Dennin et al. (2022) [43], Talhelm et al. (2015) [44] which showed relationship between intuition and political belief, ideology. The difference in brain areas also play a role [45]. But no significant relationship between intuition and norms contrast Jones (2011) [22] study results indicating people purity aspect of moral intuition was related to political attitudes. This indicates other factors influence intuition and political ideology relationship.

However, the weak relationship between political ideology dimensions and types of intuition align with Lytwyn's (2012) [23] results indicating no significant correlation between sensing-intuition, thinking-feeling and their political ideology. This indicates that personality traits alone may not affect political ideology, and there are other factors [25, 46]. Other researches offer further insight [47, 48, 49, 50, 51]. Like conservatives have high inaccurate factual beliefs, but open-minded thinking style can weaken [49], and they think more intuitively, and less analytically [47], religious belief [51], and genetics also plays a role in political preferences in both male and female [48]. But political ideology influences individual moral values [52], and was related to MBTI (Li, 2021). Conservatism was not associated to intuitive thinking styles. But open-minded thinking played important role in inaccurate beliefs [49, 51].

The psychopathy traits relationship with holistic abstract intuition contrasts the findings of Čopková and Christenková, (2021) [53]. While individuals with machiavellianism traits may look at both broad or bigger picture and pre-existing belief, mental schema while taking decisions or manipulating others. This aligns with Došenović, and Dinić (2024) [54] results, and can be reason why they process positive and negative images a lot faster [55]. But overall weak relationship between DT traits, and intuition aligns with Furnham (2022) [56] and Furnham and Crump (2014) [29]. This indicated Sensation-Intuition component of MBTI had relationship with weak dark side traits [56], and very low relationship between MBTI, HDS [29]. The other factors may play a role in relationship between DT traits and intuition [15, 27].

5. Conclusion

The study provides insights into the possible relationships between political ideology dimensions, Dark Tetrad (DT) traits, and types of intuition. The significant relationships were found between norms and certain DT traits, as well as between hierarchies and specific types of intuition. But economic ideology showed no significant relationships with DT traits, and norms with types of intuition. Additionally, some DT traits were linked to specific types of intuition,

suggesting that personality trait role in intuition. These findings contribute to understanding the psychological perspective of political ideology.

The results of this study may assist researchers in making theoretical assumptions about political ideology, DT traits and types of intuition in Indian context. It can help mental health professionals understand how mental schemas, emotional response, perspective, and dark personality traits relate with people political belief, and their views towards economy, authority role, societal and cultural norms, which in turn will help mental health professionals understand their clients better and follow more eclectic approach. This study's findings should be interpreted considering limitations, that is the potential for bias introduced by convenience sampling and self-report measures. The future studies can use large, more diverse samples with different designs to investigate cause-effect relationship, age and gender differences, and explore the factors that may influence their relationships.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest was reported.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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